

CHARACTERISTICS OF FISHERMEN COMMUNITY BEHAVIOR AND ITS RELATIONSHIP WITH THE ECONOMIC LIFE OF HOUSEHOLDS IN PANGKAJENE KEPULAUAN REGENCY, SOUTH SULAWESI

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Abstract

Pangkajene Kepulauan Regency is one of the regencies in South Sulawesi that has 115 islands, with 73 inhabited and 42 uninhabited. Among these islands, there are four sub-districts located on the islands, namely Liukang Utara, Liukang Selatan, Kalmas, and Tangaya Districts. These four sub-districts have a population of 69,272 people. The main activity of the population, as much as 87%, is fishing, so the economic life of fishermen's households depends on catching fish at sea and then selling them to intermediary traders or collecting traders. This study will examine in depth the factors that influence the economic life of fishermen households in these four sub-districts. This study is also highly relevant to identify the challenges faced by island fishermen and how they manage household life in an increasingly competitive economic condition. The results of this study can serve as a basis for designing government policies in building an economy that can support the transformation of community behavior domiciled on islands, in this case fishermen, with the orientation of eradicating poverty and stunting. The research findings related to the economic life of fishermen households in Liukang Utara and Selatan, Kalmas, and Tangaya Districts are: (1) Household income tends to fluctuate, depending on fish catches at sea; (2) High dependence on marine products without alternative sources of income; (3) Limited access to education, health, and other economic facilities; and (4) Some fishermen families are indebted to middlemen or financiers. Objective. This study aims to understand the behavioral characteristics of fishermen in Mattiro Baji Island and how these behaviors affect their household economic life. Method. This study uses the ex post facto method, which is research that measures behavioral events that occur in fishing communities. Data collection techniques include: observation, interviews, and questionnaires with fishermen in Pangkajene Kepulauan Regency. Samples were taken purposively in four sub-districts, namely Liukang Utara (60 fisherman households), Liukang Selatan (50 fisherman households), Kalmas (50 fisherman households), and Tangaya (40 fisherman households). Data analysis. The analysis used is the structural equation model (SEM) program and LISREL 8.54. This method aims to explore data in depth about fishermen's behavior and character and also to measure the relationship between household economic variables.

Keywords: Behavioral Ability, Belief, Subjective Norm, Attitude, Intention to Behave, Artisanal Fishermen Behavior.

A. INTRODUCTION

Pangkajene Kepulauan Regency, South Sulawesi, is the research area in the fisheries sector with a focus on fishing communities domiciled in Liukang Utara, Liukang Selatan, Kalmas, and Tangaya Districts with a population of 69,272 people, 617 households, and a sample of 200 fisherman households taken.

Artisanal fishermen, who are included as small-scale fisheries, are boat owners whose main income depends on fishing activities at sea, operating their boats independently with boat weights ranging from 2.75–25 GT (or boat lengths between 5 meters to 15 meters, widths between 1.5 meters to 6 meters) using simple fishing gear (such as gillnets, clown nets, mini trawls, rods, longlines), applying a profit-sharing system between the owner and crew, and selling fish catches within limited local markets (Berkes et al., 2001; Charles, 2001; Satria, 2002; Luky, 2007).

In Pangkajene Kepulauan Regency, fishing communities are considered absolutely poor, even the poorest among the poor (Mukflihati, 2010).

Various studies have also shown that fishermen, especially small-scale fisheries in Indonesia, are at a marginal level (Kusnadi, 2022; Semedi, 2003; Budi, 2008). Various efforts have been made by the government to improve fishermen's quality of life, although in implementation, the policies issued by the government often do not side with fishermen, or law enforcement is weak.

Government policies began with the Blue Revolution in the 1970s up to current legislation. In the fisheries sector, at the same time as the government issued the Green Revolution policy in agriculture, the Blue Revolution was launched as a political fisheries policy aiming to follow the success story of agriculture. The target of the Blue Revolution was the improvement of fishermen's welfare through efforts to increase efficiency and productivity in fisheries, especially marine resources, with various policy variants.

These policies included modernization with motorization and modern fishing gear, providing credit facilities in the form of business loans, engines, boats, and essential equipment to fishermen, as well as building infrastructure facilities supporting fisheries activities such as fishing ports, cold storage, fish drying places, and fish auctions (TPI). The artisanal fishing system consists of four aspects of activity (Kusnadi, 2000; Charles, 2001).

First, the use of fishing gear technology and auxiliary equipment related to capital dynamics, namely fleets, fishing gear, and auxiliaries that maximize catches with minimal environmental impact. Second, preparation and operation of fishing activities, which include fishermen's ability to determine fishing seasons, fishing locations, size and type of fish to be caught, and weather conditions suitable for going to sea.

Third, deployment of labor and capital, which includes the ability to optimize available labor and capital in operating boats and fishing gear. Fourth, maintaining the quality of catches and marketing fish, related to fishermen's ability to maintain good fish quality to achieve the highest possible selling price.

Referring to the perspective of the Theory of Planned Behavior (Ajzen, 2015), which places components of attitude, subjective norm, and perceived behavioral control as aspects influencing behavioral intention, this study aims to test the applicability of the Theory of Planned Behavior among fishermen in the western coastal area of Liukang Utara and Selatan, Pangkajene Kepulauan Regency.

The testing of this theory was conducted by:

1. Identifying factors influencing the behavioral intention of artisanal fishermen in utilizing coastal resources;
2. Determining the extent of the influence of behavioral intention on fishermen's behavior in utilizing resources; and
3. Identifying the extent of the influence of demographic characteristics on attitude, subjective norm, and perceived behavioral control among fishermen on the west coast of pangkajene kepulauan regency, south sulawesi.

B. RESEARCH METHOD

1. Design, Location, and Time. This research is a descriptive ex post facto study conducted in 14 villages within 14 sub-districts spread across 4 regencies in the northern-western coast of South Sulawesi Province. The four regencies are Barru, Pare, Maros, and Pinrang.
2. Sampling Technique. The smallest observation unit in this study is artisanal fisherman households owning boats operated independently in the selected areas. The total number of artisanal fisherman households in the northern-western coastal villages of South Sulawesi Province is 1,151 households. The sample size was determined using Slovin's formula with an error rate of 5%, resulting in 173 households.
3. Types and Data Collection Techniques. The data collected were primary data, covering demographic characteristics, attitude, subjective norm, perceived behavioral control, behavioral intention, and fishermen's behavior in fishing activities. These data were obtained through interviews using questionnaires.
4. Data Processing and Analysis. Data processing was carried out using SPSS for Windows and Lisrel 8.54. Data analysis was divided into descriptive and inferential analyses. The inferential statistical analysis used was Structural Equation Model (SEM). Model fit testing was conducted using several Goodness of Fit Test (GFT) criteria. According to Kusnendi (2008), a structural model is indicated as fit if it meets three types of GFT: (1) Chi-square test with $p\text{-value} \geq 0.05$; (2) $RMSEA \leq 0.08$; and (3) $CFI \geq 0.90$. Six variables with 57 indicators were described in the relationship between variables. The six variables were individual characteristics (X1), attitude (X2), subjective norm (X3), perceived behavioral control (X4), behavioral intention (Y1), and behavior (Y2).

C. RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Research Results

The description of the relationship between variables regarding factors influencing artisanal fishermen's behavior in fishing activities in Pangkajene Kepulauan Regency, South Sulawesi, is explained as follows:

2. Hypothesis Testing Model

- a. Hypothesis 1: “Demographic characteristics (X1) positively influence attitude (X2).” Figure 1 shows a direct influence of demographic characteristics on fishermen’s attitudes by 0.16, significant at $\alpha = 0.05$. The mathematical equation of the structural model of fishermen’s attitudes is $X2 = 0.16 X1$. Based on this, hypothesis 1 is accepted.
- b. Hypothesis 2: “Demographic characteristics (X1) positively influence subjective norm (X3).” Figure 1 shows a direct influence of demographic characteristics on fishermen’s subjective norms by 0.21, significant at $\alpha = 0.05$. The mathematical equation of the structural model of fishermen’s subjective norms is $X3 = 0.21 X1$. Based on this, hypothesis 2 is accepted.
- c. Hypothesis 3: “Demographic characteristics (X1) positively influence perceived behavioral control (X4).” Figure 1 shows a direct influence of demographic characteristics on perceived behavioral control by 0.23, significant at $\alpha = 0.05$. The mathematical equation of the structural model of fishermen’s perceived behavioral control is $X4 = 0.23 X1$. Based on this, hypothesis 3 is accepted.
- d. Hypothesis 4: “Attitude (X2), subjective norm (X3), and perceived behavioral control (X4) positively influence behavioral intention (Y1).” Figure 1 shows direct influences of attitude, subjective norm, and perceived behavioral control on behavioral intention, respectively 0.24, 0.38, and 0.40, significant at $\alpha = 0.05$. The mathematical equation of the structural model of behavioral intention is $Y1 = 0.24 X2 + 0.38 X3 + 0.40 X4$. Together, the influence of the three variables (X2, X3, and X4) on fishermen’s behavioral intention is 40 percent, significant at $\alpha = 0.05$. Based on this, hypothesis 4 is accepted.
- e. Hypothesis 5: “Behavioral intention (Y1) positively influences behavior (Y2).” Figure 1 shows the influence of behavioral intention on fishermen’s behavior by 0.51. The mathematical equation of the structural model of fishermen’s behavior is $Y2 = 0.51 Y1$. Thus, hypothesis 5 is accepted.

The Importance of Behavioral Intention on Behavior. The Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) perspective is not without criticism, especially in answering the question of how important behavioral intention is to individual behavior.

The main criticism is that TPB is considered to only predict behavior when some aspects of behavior are not under strong volitional control. Likewise, there are questions about how long the interval between behavioral intention and actual behavior is. Another criticism is that TPB assumes that humans think rationally and make systematic decisions based on sufficient information to decide to behave.

Simultaneous motives are not taken into account (Bright, 1993). To test this criticism, this study also examines the direct relationship between attitude, subjective norm, and perceived behavioral control variables with behavior variables without going through behavioral intention, using SEM analysis as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Relationship between Variable Factors Influencing the Behavior of Artisanal Fishermen in Capture Fisheries Activities in North and South Liukang Districts, Pangkep, South Sulawesi

Figure 1 above shows a model that directly examines the relationship between the attitude variable (X2), the subjective norm variable (X3), and the behavioral control belief variable (X4) toward the behavior variable (Y2).

The relationship between the attitude variable (X2) and the behavior variable (Y2) is 0.23, the relationship between the subjective norm variable (X3) and the behavior variable (Y2) is 0.22, and the relationship between the behavioral control belief variable (X4) and the behavior variable (Y2) is 0.20 with a coefficient of determination value (R²) of 0.66.

The coefficient of determination (R²) for the direct relationship of the attitude variable (X2), the subjective norm variable (X3), and the behavioral control belief variable (X4) toward the intention to behave variable (Y1) in the same model is 0.40.

Referring to the model, it can be said that the behavior of fishing communities, in addition to being positively influenced by the intention to behave, may also not be determined by the intention to behave. This research finding also reinforces the main criticism of the TPB (theory of planned behavior) perspective, which states that TPB may only be applicable when fishing communities in Liukang District and South Liukang District have sufficient information that encourages the emergence of behavioral intention.

This research observes the comparison of the coefficient of determination values between the intention to behave variable (Y1) and the behavior variable (Y2), which are 0.40 and 0.66. This shows that the tendency of the fishing community in Saugi Island, which is one of the villages where the majority of the population are fishers, to behave spontaneously (without being accompanied by an intention to behave) is greater than the behavior preceded by an intention to behave. Fishers who tend to have an intention to behave are those who already possess more comprehensive information about capture fisheries activities compared to fishers who tend to behave without being preceded by an intention to behave.

The higher coefficient of determination value of the behavior variable (Y2) compared to the intention to behave variable (Y1) indicates the lack of comprehensive information possessed by fishers regarding capture fisheries activities. This argument is reinforced by descriptive statistical findings showing the low participation of island fishers in non-formal education activities in the field of capture fisheries. Even if fishers have already behaved positively in capture fisheries activities, such behavior is more likely to be spontaneous behavior not accompanied by comprehensive knowledge of capture fisheries activities.

The existence of the intention to behave factor (even though the coefficient of determination value is smaller compared to behavior not accompanied by intention) is in line with the TPB perspective and the perspective of communication and human behavior theory. According to this theory, behavior is a human action preceded by an input process in the form of information received by each individual (Ruben, 2002), depending on whether or not the incoming information is considered important and interpreted by the individual. If considered important, the information will be stored in the individual's long-term memory. Conversely, if considered unimportant, the information will be stored in short-term memory with a high likelihood of being forgotten. The intake of information processed within an individual allows the person to have an intention to behave before engaging in the behavior.

The perspective of operant conditioning theory initiated by Skinner (Brophy, 2009) strengthens the argument for the existence of intention to behave before someone performs behavior. According to Skinner, individual behavior is the result of a learning process. For Pavlov, behavior occurs when there is a specific stimulus, while Skinner added that such behavior only explains a small part of all activities. Skinner argued that there is another form of behavior he labeled operant conditioning behavior. Skinner focused on the relationship between behavior and its consequences. For example, if pleasant, fishers will use that behavior again as often as possible. Using pleasant and unpleasant consequences in changing behavior is often called operant conditioning. Pleasant consequences will strengthen behavior, while unpleasant consequences will weaken it. Such pleasant consequences will generate an individual's behavioral intention to repeat the behavior.

The influence of the attitude variable, the subjective norm variable, and the behavioral control belief variable on the intention to behave variable ($R^2 = 0.40$) indicates the existence of other variables amounting to 60% outside of attitude, subjective norms, and behavioral control beliefs that affect the intention to behave variable. Similarly, the influence of the intention to behave variable on the behavior variable at 0.51 indicates that fishers' behavioral intentions in

conducting fishing activities do not fully align with the behavior they perform. In line with the concept of agency and structure, Kusnadi's (2000) research also emphasizes the structural factors that cause fishers to remain poor. These factors can be categorized into internal (micro) and external (macro) factors. Internal factors are those related to fishers' human resources and work activities, namely (1) limited quality of human resources, (2) limited business capital capacity and fishing technology, (3) working relationships (boat owners–labor fishers), (4) difficulty diversifying fishing businesses, (5) high dependence on the fishing occupation, and (6) lifestyles less oriented toward the future.

External factors are those related to conditions outside the fishers and their work activities, including (1) development policies more oriented toward productivity to support national economic growth, partial and not in favor of traditional fishers, (2) fishery product marketing systems that favor intermediaries, (3) coastal and marine ecosystem damage due to land-based pollution, (4) fishing practices using chemicals, coral reef destruction, and mangrove forest conversion in coastal areas, (5) the use of environmentally unfriendly fishing gear, (6) limited post-harvest fish processing technology, (7) limited employment opportunities in non-fisheries sectors available in fishing villages, (8) natural conditions and seasonal fluctuations that prevent fishers from going to sea throughout the year, and (9) geographical isolation of fishing villages that hampers the mobility of goods, services, capital, and people.

In the context of research findings on artisanal fishers' behavior in Pangkajene Regency, particularly in North Liukang District and South Liukang District, artisanal capture fishers are also one of the important stakeholders as actors directly engaged in the exploitation of fishery resources. Amid the increasing degradation of fishery resources in the western coastal waters of Pangkajene Regency, South Sulawesi, the fishing grounds are increasingly limited due to the complex use of marine areas, uncertainty of natural conditions (weather), as well as regulatory uncertainty in favor of fishers and weak enforcement of such regulations. Artisanal fishers in the western coastal area must engage in capture fisheries activities to meet their economic and social needs.

The research findings show that the character attached to fishing communities includes: hardworking, dependent on nature, traditional knowledge, and a high sense of mutual cooperation. However, it also confirms the greater tendency for the characteristics of fishers living in the two districts (North Liukang and South Liukang, Pangkajene Regency, South Sulawesi) not preceded by behavioral intention, which may result in uncertainty in household economic life. Thus, the descriptive behavior of fishers in capture fisheries activities is at an average positive score, yet such behavior still needs to be strengthened with information intake in the form of fisher empowerment programs to achieve a highly positive behavioral score. The existence of behavioral intention before fishers engage in behavior in capture fisheries activities can become an entry point in designing learning processes for fishers, which will subsequently determine their welfare levels. The Fisheries Management Flow and the Urgency of Research **Findings in Pangkajene Regency are illustrated in Figure 2 below.**

Figure 2: Involvement of Many Parties in Fisheries Management and the Urgency of Findings from the Study of Artisanal Fishermen's Behavior in Utilizing Fisheries Resources in South Sulawesi (Berkes, et al., 2025), (Adrianto, et al. 2025)

D. CONCLUSION

Based on the research results and discussion presented in the previous section, it can be concluded that the theory of planned behavior perspective with the ex post facto method is used to observe the intention to behave and the behavior of artisanal fishermen in Pangkajene Regency, although it is possible that certain behaviors are carried out without going through the intention to behave. Demographic characteristic factors directly influence attitudes, the level of compliance, and the competence of fishermen in capture fisheries activities. Factors of attitude, compliance level, and competence directly influence the intention of fishermen to behave in capture fisheries activities.

The factor of intention to behave directly influences the behavior of fishermen in capture fisheries activities. The coefficient of determination between the variables of attitude, compliance level, and competence toward the intention to behave variable is 0.40. This condition indicates the existence of other variable factors amounting to 60% outside of this research that affect the intention to behave. Meanwhile, the influence of the intention to behave variable on behavior, amounting to 0.51, indicates that not all of fishermen's intentions to behave are realized in accordance with their behavior in capture fisheries activities. This research finding, which explains the factors that influence the behavior of artisanal fishermen in the utilization of fishery resources, can contribute to fisheries co-management activities in Indonesia, particularly in fishing community groups in the South Sulawesi Province.

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